

THE ANNUAL CATALOGUE OF PLANT IMMIGRANTS

Many Additions to Our Food Plants are Being Made by Office of Seed and Plant Introduction—To be Available Gratis to all Serious Experimenters Who File Application

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THE war is demonstrating in a striking way the danger of being too practical. The technical knowledge required today to fight this war is touching everywhere the borderland of knowledge as never before, and there is hardly a specialist, no matter how narrow the field is in which he works, but has been called upon to furnish information of some sort.

Mankind has become willing as never before to listen to every suggestion and follow up every clue which may lead to important discoveries bearing on the war.

Changes in agriculture will necessarily come with the changes in transportation and the perfection of the farm tractor.

In order to get ready for these changes much experimentation will be required and thousands of men on their own places are needed to do this work. To expect this work to be done by state experiment stations and the Government agencies, and wait for these men to do it, would be like waiting upon the Government to discover the aerial highway. Individual initiative flew the first aeroplane and individual hybridizers will originate many new plant varieties.

The Government, through its Office of Foreign Seed and Plant Introduction, brings in every year several thousand species and varieties of plants, gathered from different parts of the world. These are for a wide trial in those parts of the country where they are likely to thrive.

The seventh Annual List of these plant immigrants is appearing in a few days and will be sent to *bona fide* experimenters all over the country. A few photographs, illustrating some of the economic and ornamental plants described in this 1917 Annual List are reproduced here in the Journal. There are 1400 interesting new plant introductions contained in this Annual List and applicants for it will be supplied up to the limit of the edition.

All plants listed are sent out gratis, on request, after adequate information has been received proving the capabilities of the applicant to take care of and experiment with these rare species and varieties.

It should be kept in mind that all plants described are newcomers to this country, and are, for this reason, experimental. No one should imagine that immediate profits are to be made out of them, and those whose interest is chiefly in the money end of the problem—who are first of all practical and after that plant lovers or investigators—will be too impatient for results to make good experimenters and cooperators of the Office of Seed and Plant Introduction.

Everyone who really loves, and knows how to grow and care for new plants, should get in touch with the Office referred to, and if the supply holds out get a limited number of the new introductions which in the opinion of the office experts have a good chance of succeeding.

ORCHARD OF HARDY OLIVES IN THE CRIMEA

An Olive Orchard at Nikita, in the Crimea, which has stood practically uniniured temperatures of -2° F. at intervals for 60 or 70 years. (S. P. I. No. 27172.) Seedlings from this orchard should show unusual hardiness and may succeed in sections where other olive varieties have failed. (Fig. 6.)

As explained in the Annual List, all plants sent out are accompanied with special descriptive permanent labels, which are a great help to experimenters in keeping fresh in their minds the particular uses for which the plants were introduced.

Correspondence should be addressed to the Office of Foreign Seed and Plant Introduction, Bureau of Plant Industry, United States Department of Agriculture, Washington, D. C.

The following information is necessary and must be supplied on special Experimenters' Cards which will be sent to applicants on their request, be-

fore requests for plant material can be filled:

Permanent address: All plants are sent out by parcel post, not by express. Do you wish plant material sent to above address? If not, fill out permanent mail address for plant material. How much land have you available for experimental planting and how much do you wish to devote to such planting? Is this land owned or leased by you? Have you a water supply for irrigation purposes? Have you a green house? Are you interested in experimenting with: Grains; forage plants; fruit trees; small fruits; vegetables; shade trees; ornamental trees or shrubs; perennial flowering plants; annual flowering plants; house plants? If so, state below which you are especially interested in. Give your experience in caring for and experimenting with plants.

THE MURASAKI VARIETY OF JAPANESE FLOWERING CHERRY

The double-flowered cherry trees of Japan are preeminently trees for dooryards and small parks, and should be planted near garden walks, so that people can walk under them and enjoy close at hand the loveliness of their exquisitely delicate coloring. They are no more showy than our crab-apples when seen at a distance. The Murasaki (*Prunus serrulata*) S. P. I. No. 45056, is a deep-pink mid-season, very free-flowering variety (April 20 in Maryland). The blossom centers turn red with age, and the petals fall in great abundance turning the ground pink beneath the trees. In autumn the foliage turns a golden yellow. Photographed by Fairchild, twice natural size. (Fig. 7.)

THE OJOCHIN VARIETY OF JAPANESE FLOWERING CHERRY

Although this variety of *Prunus serrulata*, S. P. I. No. 45051, is not so profuse a bloomer as many of the strictly double-flowered varieties, its large, almost white blossoms, which are often quite single, remind one in their beauty of single roses, and when scattered over the branches, of a large-sized tree, as they usually are, they produce when viewed from below, a most impressive sight. It is a late flowering variety, May 1 in Maryland. Photographed by Fairchild, twice natural size in order to emphasize the beauty of the flowers. (Fig. 8.)

THE JAPANESE MUME OR UME

As a spring-flowering tree, the Japanese apricot (*Prunus mume*) or Japanese plum, as the mume is incorrectly called, is perhaps the favorite of the Japanese poets even more than the flowering cherry. It often blooms so early that the snows fall on the fragrant blossoms. The fruits remind one of the American wild goose plum in flavor but are much better keepers. They are preserved and made into jelly and put down in salt while still green. These salted or pickled mumes are among the sourest pickles known and are excellent with meats. They form a part of the Japanese soldiers' ration, and are said to quench thirst on long marches. Many varieties of these mumes are recognized in Japan. The illustration is of fruits produced at Chico, Cal. Five-year-old trees have borne in Maryland also. Photographed natural size. (Fig. 9.)

THE MU HSIN HUNG JUJUBE

An attractive medium-sized variety, S. P. I. No. 22684, collected by Frank N. Meyer at Tsintse, Shansi, China. Of good flavor and texture. The tree does not appear to be as heavy a bearer as smaller fruited varieties but it grows in China to a very large size with few side branches on the main limbs and has no spines. When processed the Jujube compares favorably with the date. Photographed natural size. (Fig. 10.)

THE CHINGCHOWFU JUJUBE

This variety, S. P. I. No. 30488, was introduced by the Rev. W. M. Hayes of Chingchowfu, China, and is said to be the largest variety of that region. The trees at Chico, Cal., have borne well and the quality of the fruits is excellent. Before ripening they are covered with brown blotches, which spread rapidly until the whole fruit is brown. As Mr. Hayes did not give the Chinese name for this variety the place name has been chosen. Photographed natural size. (Fig. 11).

A REMARKABLE PUCKERLESS PERSIMMON OF THE GOSHO CLASS

The greatest drawback to the persimmon has always been its astringency, which has made it necessary to ripen it until too soft to be eaten out of hand. This new variety which has first been fruited out in this country by H. Harold Hume of Glen St. Mary's, Fla., can be eaten while still as hard as an apple, and is then as delicious in flavor, and fine in texture, as the best of the soft varieties. It has a richer flavor than the Tamopan and appears to be more reliably tannin free, at least in Florida. S. P. I. 26773. Photographed three-fourths natural size. (Fig. 12.)

A NEW TYPE OF FRUITING CHERRY FROM CHINA

The Tanghsi cherry (*Prunus pseudocerasus*) S. P. I. 18587, orchards of which were shown to Mr. F. N. Meyer by the Rev. A. Kennedy, near the village of Tanghsi; in Chekiang province, has been identified as the true *Prunus pseudocerasus* of Lindley, under which name the Japanese flowering cherries have been commonly but erroneously known for seventy years. It appears that horticulturally, owing perhaps to the confusion in names, no attention has ever been given in America to this remarkable Chinese species of cherry. It turns out to be ten days earlier in fruiting than any other in northern California, and of sufficiently good quality without further improvement to attract commercial attention. The illustration shows a three-year-old bud on Mahaleb stock. (Fig. 13.)